

MIGRATION PROCESSES OF THE ARMENIAN DIASPORA IN THE TERRITORY OF OUR REGION AND THE HISTORICAL

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Abstract. *This article examines the historical processes of the formation of the Armenian diaspora in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its contribution to the country's socio-economic transformation. Particular attention is paid to the legal aspects of ethnopolitics and to ensuring equal opportunities for the development of all peoples residing in the republic. The study also addresses the establishment and development of national cultural centers that contribute to the preservation and promotion of distinctive culture and traditions, as well as maintaining connections with the historical homeland, using the Armenian diaspora as an illustrative example.*

Keywords: *Uzbekistan, ethnopolitics, national cultural centers, ethnic groups, culture, traditions, interethnic relations, human rights.*

Introduction

The issue of interethnic interaction and the sustainability of multiethnic societies has gained particular academic relevance in the 21st century. The intensification of migration flows, the transnationalization of social processes, and the formation of diasporas require profound theoretical reflection and interdisciplinary analysis. Modern states inevitably face the need to develop policies that ensure the harmonious coexistence of diverse ethnocultural communities integrated into a unified socio-political space. The causes of migration processes are always multifaceted and depend on various factors, including political, economic, social, and complex environmental conditions, all of which influence migration changes not only within individual countries but globally. Over the past centuries, these processes have intensified and, in some cases, have generated irreversible transformations leading to significant structural changes.

Wars increasingly acquire a destructive character, producing forced migration processes accompanied by large-scale resettlements and the disruption of established social structures. These include interethnic and interstate conflicts, the consequences of which are expressed in the destabilization of the socio-political environment, increased social tension, and the escalation of forced migration. Economic crises and periods of decline often compel populations to engage in internal and external mobility in search of more acceptable working conditions.

In the pursuit of alternative sources of income, people are forced to change their economic strategies, adopt new forms of employment, and thereby inadvertently transform the socio-economic environment of the state. Environmental factors and disasters also represent a significant cause of migration, leading to environmental degradation, loss of vital resources, and the creation of unfavorable living conditions. Despite these negative factors, migration processes also have positive effects, as they contribute to the redistribution of labor resources, stimulate the economic development of host regions, and expand intercultural communication.

Uzbekistan represents a vivid example of a country where unique models of interethnic harmony have been formed over many centuries. A large number of peoples who migrated to the country in the 20th century found a second homeland there and made an invaluable contribution to

its development. Among the many ethnic groups residing in Uzbekistan, the Armenian diaspora occupies a special place. Its historical trajectory, cultural contribution, and contemporary forms of self-organization are of considerable research interest from both theoretical and practical perspectives.

The study of diasporas constitutes one of the key areas of contemporary ethnology, political science, and sociology. A diaspora is understood as a stable ethnocultural community that maintains ties with its historical homeland while being integrated into the social structure of the host country. The contemporary issues of ethno-political research are of significant scholarly interest, as they are directly intertwined with the major challenges and transformations of the modern world. Within the framework of this study, an attempt was made to analyze the sociocultural characteristics of diaspora communities functioning within the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as to identify the specifics of their adaptation to changing socio-economic and political conditions of the host state. The present work seeks to present the results obtained from the study of the historical prerequisites for the formation and evolution of national ethnic groups residing in the country, with particular focus on the Armenian diaspora.

In the second half of the 20th century, the term “diaspora” (with the Armenian equivalent “spyurk”) became a commonly accepted and widely used designation in European languages for Armenians living outside their national state. The term is actively employed both in academic discourse and in public and everyday usage. The relevance of the selected topic is determined by the growing role of diasporas in both the socio-political life of host countries and the development of their historical homelands. Migration processes, whose roots extend deep into antiquity, are shaped by a complex combination of social, economic, confessional, and other factors.

Contemporary practice demonstrates that diasporas, as a rule, rapidly integrate into the sociocultural space of host countries and actively participate in various spheres of their socio-political and economic life. In this regard, the study of the historical prerequisites for the formation of the Armenian diaspora in Uzbekistan, as well as its institutional structure, allows for a deeper understanding of the specifics of diaspora functioning and for determining their significance within the political system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Within the conducted research, the primary methodological tool was the general scientific method of content analysis. Its application made it possible to systematize and interpret a wide range of sources, identify the essential characteristics of the category “diaspora,” and determine the degree of involvement of ethnic groups in the political processes of contemporary Uzbekistan. Based on the analysis of the regulatory and legal framework, official annual reports, documentary materials, and the historical experience of the formation of the Armenian diaspora, the main patterns of its adaptation, institutionalization, and participation in the socio-political life of the state were identified.

The earliest evidence of the presence of Armenians in Central Asia dates back to the 3rd–4th centuries CE. Their migration was primarily associated with the spread of Christianity and the persecution of adherents of the new religion in the Roman Empire and Sasanian Iran. Armenia was among the first states to adopt Christianity as a state religion, which contributed to the active movement of Armenian spiritual missions eastward. Individual representatives of the Armenian people, primarily merchants and Christian missionaries, settled permanently in Central Asia, gradually integrating into the region’s socio-economic structures. A significant number of Armenians also arrived in Central Asian lands as part of military formations of Iran and Parthia. Historical sources indicate that in 599, the Iranian Shah appointed the Armenian military

commander Smbat Bagratuni as commander of the Armenian-Persian army and dispatched him on a military campaign aimed at subjugating Kushan territories.

Armenian missionaries and merchants followed the routes of the Great Silk Road, forming early Christian settlements. Archaeological evidence discovered, for example, in Old Termez, indicates the existence of Christian cult complexes dating to the 7th–8th centuries, executed in architectural traditions characteristic of Armenian ecclesiastical architecture.

During the Timurid era, Armenians actively resettled in Samarkand and other cities of the region. Amir Timur brought Armenian craftsmen, including builders, jewelers, weaponsmiths, and stonecutters, which contributed to the development of craft quarters and the strengthening of economic ties. Chronicles of European travelers confirm the presence of extensive Armenian settlements in Samarkand. In subsequent centuries, Armenians continued to arrive in Central Asia independently as merchants, artisans, scholars, and entrepreneurs, establishing stable connections with the cities of the Bukhara and Kokand Khanates.

The incorporation of Turkestan into the Russian Empire in the second half of the 19th century became an important stage in the consolidation of Armenian communities. The construction of the Krasnovodsk–Samarkand railway expanded migration opportunities. Despite attempts by the tsarist administration to limit the flow of settlers due to concerns over the strengthening of Armenian entrepreneurial activity, the Armenian population steadily increased. Armenian schools, craft workshops, trading enterprises, hotels, wineries, and brick factories emerged in cities. Armenians actively occupied positions in state institutions and the army.

According to statistical data, by 1895, 167 Armenians resided in the Samarkand region, of whom 161 lived in Samarkand; the overwhelming majority, 153 individuals, were men. Although in the first decades after the region's incorporation into the Russian Empire the Armenian population in the Samarkand and Fergana regions was relatively small compared to other areas of Central Asia, a significant increase was observed between 1902 and 1913. During this period, the Armenian population of the Fergana region increased by 2,130 people, reaching 3,292 residents, of whom 1,602 lived in urban areas and 1,690 in rural areas. These data demonstrate that despite restrictions imposed by the tsarist administration, Armenian migration to the Turkestan region continued to intensify. Accordingly, their economic and social activities expanded, including the establishment of workshops, factories, wineries, baths, hotels, revenue houses, restaurants, and commercial establishments founded by members of the Armenian community. A significant number of Armenians held positions in state and military service.

From the late 19th century, Armenian-Gregorian parish schools began to operate in the territory of present-day Uzbekistan. The educational process in these institutions, with the exception of religious instruction, was regulated with mandatory use of the Russian language. In the early 20th century, the Armenian diaspora gradually strengthened its economic positions, which contributed to a noticeable increase in its level of prosperity. In 1908, an Armenian-Gregorian church was built in Tashkent, becoming an important center of the religious and cultural life of the community. In the early 1920s, the Armenian Central Bureau was established in the Turkestan Republic, under whose auspices educational and cultural institutions were successively created, including 13 schools, three preschool institutions, a club, and three libraries.

During the Soviet period, the size of the Armenian diaspora in Uzbekistan continued to grow due to natural population increase, migration of individual families, and organized resettlement from the Armenian SSR. By the 1970s, more than 50,000 Armenians resided in the largest cities of the republic, including Tashkent, Samarkand, Kokand, Andijan, and Bukhara, indicating the deep-

rooted presence and institutionalization of the community within Uzbekistan's socio-economic space. The Soviet era marked a period of intensive growth for the Armenian community in Uzbekistan. Migration from the Armenian SSR, economic modernization, urban development, and industrial expansion contributed to the increase in the diaspora's population. By the 1970s, Armenians lived in nearly all major cities of the republic, numbering several tens of thousands.

During this period, Armenians made a substantial contribution to science, culture, education, and industry. Among the most prominent figures were Tamara Khanum, Nikolai Karakhan, Oganés Tatevosyan, Anatoly Petrosyants, and many others. Contemporary Uzbekistan is a multicultural state inhabited by representatives of more than 120 nationalities. Constitutional norms guarantee equality of citizens regardless of ethnic affiliation or religious belief. National policy is aimed at supporting cultural diversity, strengthening interethnic harmony, and developing diaspora organizations.

The community plays an important role in maintaining cultural identity and integrating youth. The first Armenian cultural center was established in Tashkent in 1989. Later, the centers of Samarkand and Andijan were unified into the Armenian National Cultural Center of Uzbekistan, which became a clear confirmation of the consistent state policy aimed at supporting and developing the spiritual and cultural needs of the republic's citizens. The Center implements a wide range of social, youth, interethnic, and cultural programs. Since 1993, a linguistic circle has functioned at the Center, providing opportunities for those interested to study the basics of the Armenian language and the 1,600-year-old written tradition of the Armenian people.

The Armenian National Cultural Center hosts studios of fine and applied arts "Arvest," the choreographic studio "Erebuni," and the drama studio "Dar." The Center's sports section initiated mini-football tournaments among national cultural centers, with the team "Apaga" winning the competition three times. Since 2006, the journal of Armenians of Uzbekistan "Depi Apaga" ("Toward the Future") has been published, inspired by Charles Aznavour. During his participation in the international festival "Sharq Taronalari," he met with representatives of the Armenian community of Uzbekistan, which contributed to the further development of cultural initiatives. At the initiative of the journal's editorial board, the "Our Hearth" club operates, organizing literary and musical evenings held at the House-Museum of Tamara Khanum and enjoying considerable popularity among the general public of the capital.

The history of the Armenian diaspora in Uzbekistan is a history of centuries-long interaction, cultural mutual influence, and joint creative endeavor. Over many centuries, Armenians have been active participants in the political, economic, and cultural processes of the region. Their contribution has become an integral part of Uzbekistan's historical heritage.

Conclusion

Modern Uzbekistan, while maintaining its commitment to the principles of interethnic harmony, provides the Armenian community with conditions for the development of cultural autonomy and the implementation of public initiatives. The experience of the Armenian diaspora demonstrates a successful model of integration based on mutual respect, legal protection, and cultural dialogue. The research findings obtained may be used for further theoretical study of the role of diasporas, their influence on political systems, and the dynamics of interethnic relations in contemporary societies.

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